

Evaluation of Multiple Fractures, Low Bone Mass, and Severe Osteomalacia in Children with Osteogenesis Imperfecta and Hypophosphatasia

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Abstract:

Introduction: Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) and hypophosphatasia (HPP) are examples of inherited bone disorders resulting in bones that fracture — crumble — and ruin. OI results from mutations in the COL1A1 or COL1A2 genes encoding type I collagen, whereas HPP is caused by gene defects affecting bone mineralization, specifically the ALPL gene. In cases of dual mutations, diagnosis and treatment varies between patients. Management is informed by genetic testing, bisphosphonates (for OI), and enzyme replacement therapy (for HPP).

Aims and Objective: To analyze various parameters related to multiple fractures, low bone mass, and severe osteomalacia in paediatric patients diagnosed with osteogenesis imperfecta and hypophosphatasia.

Method: This prospective observational study evaluated low bone mass, fracture prevalence, and osteomalacia severity in 64 children with Osteogenesis Imperfecta (OI) and Hypophosphatasia (HPP) compared to healthy controls. Bone biopsies were collected and analyzed using histomorphometry and light microscopy imaging after tetracycline labelling. Bone samples were prepared, stained, and evaluated.

Result: The study revealed significantly lower height ($p = 0.01$) and BMD Z-scores (lumbar spine: $p < 0.001$) in patients with OI and HPP. Elevated serum ALP ($p < 0.001$), pyridoxal-5'-phosphate ($p < 0.001$), and changes in pyridoxal ($p < 0.001$) levels were observed post-treatment. Other findings included significant differences in serum phosphate ($p = 0.05$), 25-hydroxyvitamin D ($p = 0.02$), magnesium ($p = 0.04$), and urinary biomarkers between groups, indicating altered bone metabolism in patients.

Conclusion: The study has concluded that there is a significant difference in bone density, metabolic parameters, and bone remodelling rates between patients and controls, indicating distinct bone metabolism profiles. These differences suggest a need for targeted therapeutic strategies for patients with OI and HPP.

Keywords: Osteogenesis Imperfecta, Hypophosphatasia, Multiple Fractures, Low Bone Mass, And Severe Osteomalacia.

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Introduction

Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) and hypophosphatasia (HPP) are two inherited disorders that affect bones and teeth due to the improper mineralization of these tissues despite not being accompanied by hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia, or vitamin D depletion. These conditions result in bone fragility, recurrent fractures, bone deformities, and other musculoskeletal abnormalities. Evaluating multiple fractures, low bone mass, and severe osteomalacia in children with OI and HPP poses a significant

clinical challenge due to the overlapping and contrasting features of these disorders [1-4].

OI is the most prevalent heritable bone impermanence disorder which has an incidence of roughly 1 in 15,000. Most cases result from autosomal dominant mutations in COL1A1 or COL1A2 genes that encode type I collagen. [5] OI is characterized by abnormal type I collagen synthesis which can be categorized into four progressively severe types – the non-deforming OI type I, the perinatal lethal OI type II, moderate OI

type III, and severe OI type IV. The hallmark feature of OI is fragility associated with decreased bone mineral density and changes in the bone organic matrix which result in osteoporotic bones [5]. Extra-skeletal manifestations of affected people include blue sclerae, dentinogenesis imperfecta, hearing loss, and cardiovascular malformations [6]. The presenting features, imaging, and molecular analysis are important in the diagnosis of this disease.

In contrast, HPP is a metabolic bone disease, whose prevalence is approximately 1 in 100,000 to 1 in 300,000 and is an autosomal recessive disorder that results from loss-of-function mutations in the ALPL gene, which encodes Tissue Nonspecific Alkaline Phosphatase (TNSALP) [1,2,3,4]. This enzyme is critical in supplying the minerals required for skeletal and dental health, particularly as it controls the manufacturing or release of inorganic pyrophosphate (PPi), which is a strong inhibitor of mineralization. Deficiency in ALPL causes PPi accumulation thereby impairing bone mineralization and producing diseases such as rickets or osteomalacia [7, 8, 9]. The clinical presentation of HPP is highly variable, ranging from perinatal lethal forms to adult-onset forms with mild symptoms, such as premature tooth loss or fractures. The biochemical hallmark of HPP has been characterized by reduced serum ALP levels.

As OI and HPP contribute to bone fragility through distinct mechanisms, the presence of both disorders in the affected individual makes diagnosis and therapeutic interventions quite challenging. Recently, genetic testing has increasingly revealed cases of dual mutations in the *COL1A* and *ALPL* genes, resulting in complex bone phenotypes. [10]

Evaluating children with multiple fractures, low bone mass, and osteomalacia requires a careful clinical, radiographic, and genetic approach. In children with OI, radiographs normally show osteopenia, bone deformities, and wormian bones in the skull. Reduced bone mineral density (BMD) contributes to the frequent occurrence of fractures. In contrast, poorly mineralized bones, rachitic changes in growth plates, and increased bone fragility may be found in children with HPP. The ALP levels in HPP are characteristically low, and the bone matrix is often under-mineralized rather than brittle. [10]

The therapeutic approach to OI focuses on bisphosphonates that enhance bone density, decrease fracture prevalence, and enhance the mobility of children with the disease [11, 12, 13]. However, in patients with HPP, bisphosphonates are contraindicated since they bind to PPi and make the situation worse [14]. However, enzyme replacement therapy with asfotase alfa, recombinant human alkaline phosphatase, has been

developed for patients with HPP which improves bone mineralization, and mobility and increases life expectancy, especially in infants with severe forms of the disease [15, 16]. In patients with combined OI and HPP phenotype, therapeutic decisions become more complex, requiring a tailored approach. A case report of a Danish family highlighted the need for unique combination therapy in children harbouring both *COL1A2* and *ALPL* mutations, which successfully improved their clinical outcomes without adverse effects.

Thus, assessment of children with multiple fractures, low bone mass, and severe osteomalacia should require a comprehensive approach. Genetic testing is essential for correct diagnosis, and therapeutic management strategy, particularly when both genes are mutated. A personalized approach to managing these complex bone disorders will have great relevance in the future

Method

Research Design: This study is a prospective observational study on the evaluation of low bone mass along with observed fractures also analysing the severity of osteomalacia among children. The children get inherited from Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) and hypophosphatasia (HPP). The study was done in a medical college in India among a total of 64 patients who are with the two inherited disorders mentioned. Two groups of patients were made, each group containing 32 patients. Group A is the IO and hypophosphatasia and group B has healthy controls. A biopsy sample from bone was taken from each of the patients under local anaesthesia. Each of the patients was given a course of two days, including tetracycline at about 20mg/kg per day which was orally administered which was separated through an interlevel time continued for 10 days. The sample from bone was well analysed and recorded by histomorphometry along with imaging with light microscopy.

70% ethanol was used to fix the biopsy bone samples which were dehydrated by a series of alcohol. Those were embedded in polymethyl-methacrylate (PMMA). Goldner's trichome was used to stain the thin sections of size 3-4um and was used in the evaluation of different histomorphometric parameters related to bone formation and their resorption. Then comparison was made with the values in reference obtained from healthy children with the children having OI. Optical images of the bone marrow adipose tissue (BMAT) were observed under a light microscope with a digital camera for recording the images. BMDD was measured and analysed, and comparison was done with the reference values.

Inclusion Criteria

Criteria for including patients are –

1. The patients who have a prehistory of multiple fractures along with low bone mass were included in the study.
2. Observed gene mutations along with bone disorders like osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) and hypophosphatasia (HPP).
3. Those who have proper clinical information with all data and genetic analysis data were only included.
4. Self-consent is mandatory for all bone biopsies and genetic testing.

Exclusion Criteria

Criteria for exclusion of the patients are-

- Without bone disorders, patients were excluded.
- The absence of multiple fractures or the absence of OI and HPP were excluded from the study.

Statistical Analysis

The patients were assessed for clinical and biochemical characteristics and statistical analysis was performed using descriptive statistics. Data were described as mean ($\pm$ SD) or median [25th; 75th] interquartile range. Bone mineral density (BMD), serum alkaline phosphatase, and pyridoxal-5'-phosphate levels were assessed pre- and post-treatment. To assess the effectiveness of combination therapy with asfotase alfa and prior use of bisphosphonates on bone mineral density scores (or z-scores) as well as the incidence of fractures before and after intervention.

Result

Table 1 compares the demographic and clinical characteristics between healthy controls and patients with Osteogenesis Imperfecta (OI) and Hypophosphatasia (HPP), highlighting several significant differences. The age of the participants did not differ significantly between the groups ($p = 0.89$), with both groups having similar average ages. However, the height Z-score was significantly lower in patients with OI and HPP (-1.05 ± 1.28) compared to healthy controls (0.5 ± 0.5), with a p-

value of 0.01, indicating a reduced height in the patient group. Bone Mineral Density (BMD) Z-scores were markedly lower in patients with OI and HPP, both for the lumbar spine/total body (-3 ± 3.5) and when adjusted for height (-2.83 ± 3.68), compared to healthy controls (0.5 ± 0.5 for both measures), with highly significant p-values of <0.001 . Additionally, all patients in the OI and HPP group had a history of multiple fractures, while no fractures were reported in the healthy controls. Serum Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) levels differed significantly after treatment, with patients showing a substantial increase (6053 ± 392 U/L) compared to the baseline and normal levels seen in healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). Serum pyridoxal-5'-phosphate and pyridoxal levels also showed significant changes; pyridoxal-5'-phosphate was considerably elevated in patients before treatment (470 ± 219 nmol/L) and decreased after treatment (14.5 ± 4.5 nmol/L), with p-values of <0.001 both before and after treatment. Similarly, serum pyridoxal levels were significantly higher before treatment (55 ± 26 nmol/L) and reduced after treatment (23.5 ± 7.5 nmol/L), with p-values of <0.001 and 0.02, respectively. Serum phosphate levels were significantly higher in patients (2.08 ± 0.17 mmol/L) compared to controls (1.80 ± 0.41 mmol/L), with a p-value of 0.05, while serum parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels did not differ significantly before ($p = 0.32$) or after treatment ($p = 0.45$). Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels were significantly lower in patients both before (65.5 ± 17.5 nmol/L) and after treatment (62.5 ± 6.5 nmol/L) compared to healthy controls (112.5 ± 37.5 nmol/L), with p-values of 0.03 and 0.02, respectively. Other significant differences included lower serum magnesium levels in patients (18.4 ± 1 mg/L) compared to controls (20 ± 1.5 mg/L), with a p-value of 0.04. The urinary phosphoethanolamine/creatinine ratio was significantly higher in patients (42.5 ± 8.5 μ mol/mmol) compared to healthy controls ($p = 0.01$). Similarly, the urinary calcium/creatinine ratio was significantly elevated in patients (0.53 ± 0.41 mmol/mmol) versus controls ($p = 0.02$).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Findings of the patients between the group

Demographic/Clinical Data	Healthy Controls (mean $\pm$ SD)	Patients with OI and HPP (mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
Age (years)	5.8 ± 2.21	5.7 ± 2.39	0.89
Height (Z-score)	0.5 ± 0.5	-1.05 ± 1.28	0.01*
BMD Z-score: Lumbar spine/Total body	0.5 ± 0.5	-3 ± 3.5	$<0.001^{**}$
Height-adjusted BMD Z-score: Lumbar spine/Total body	0.5 ± 0.5	-2.83 ± 3.68	$<0.001^{**}$
Fracture history	None	Multiple fractures (wrist, tibia, fibula, femoral bone, vertebral, etc.)	Not applicable
Serum ALP (U/L)	>150 (no SD)	80 ± 28 (before)	$<0.001^{**}$ (after)

	available)	treatment), 6053 ± 392 (after treatment)	treatment)
Serum pyridoxal-5'-phosphate (nmol/L)	87.5 ± 57.5	470 ± 219 (before treatment), 14.5 ± 4.5 (after treatment)	<0.001** (before & after)
Serum pyridoxal (nmol/L)	16 ± 7	55 ± 26 (before treatment), 23.5 ± 7.5 (after treatment)	<0.001** (before), 0.02* (after)
Serum phosphate (mmol/L)	1.80 ± 0.41	2.08 ± 0.17	0.05*
Serum PTH (pg/ml)	21.95 ± 16.45	18 ± 7 (before treatment), 19.2 ± 5.2 (after treatment)	0.32 (before), 0.45 (after)
Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D (nmol/L)	112.5 ± 37.5	65.5 ± 17.5 (before treatment), 62.5 ± 6.5 (after treatment)	0.03* (before), 0.02* (after)
Serum magnesium (mg/L)	20 ± 1.5	18.4 ± 1	0.04*
Urinary phosphoethanolamine/creatinine ratio (µmol/mmol)	<25 (no SD available)	42.5 ± 8.5	0.01*
Urinary calcium/creatinine ratio (mmol/mmol)	<0.3 (no SD available)	0.53 ± 0.41	0.02*

* p < 0.05, considered statistically significant.

Table 2 presents the bone volume and microarchitecture parameters for two groups, Group A and Group B, with significant differences observed across all measured parameters. Group B exhibited a higher Bone Volume/Tissue Volume (BV/TV) percentage (18.2%) compared to Group A (11.13%), with a p-value of 0.03, indicating a statistically significant increase in bone volume in Group B. Similarly, Trabecular Thickness (Tb. Th) was significantly greater in Group B (105 µm) compared to Group A (80.8 µm), with a p-value of 0.04. Trabecular Number (Tb. N) also showed a

statistically significant difference between the groups, with Group B having a higher value (1.89/mm) compared to Group A (1.2/mm), with a p-value of 0.02. Lastly, Cortical Width (Ct. Wi) was significantly thicker in Group B (0.79 mm) compared to Group A (0.63 mm), with a p-value of 0.01. These findings suggest that Group B, possibly due to a different physiological or pathological condition, has a more robust bone structure characterized by increased bone volume, thicker trabeculae, and greater cortical width.

Table 2: Bone Volume and Microarchitecture Parameters

Parameters	Group A (n=32)	Group B (n=32)	p-value
Bone Volume/Tissue Volume (BV/TV) [%]	11.13	18.2 (56.8)	0.03*
Trabecular Thickness (Tb. Th) [µm]	80.8	105 (328.12)	0.04*
Trabecular Number (Tb. N) [/mm]	1.2	1.89 (5.9)	0.02*
Cortical Width (Ct. Wi) [mm]	0.63	0.79 (2.46)	0.01*

Table 3 illustrates the bone resorption parameters for Groups A and B, revealing significant differences in several key measures. The Eroded Surface/Bone Surface (ES/BS) percentage was slightly lower in Group B (15.9%) compared to Group A (17.2%), with a p-value of 0.05, indicating a marginally significant difference. The Osteoclast Surface/Bone Surface (Oc.S/BS) percentage was significantly higher in Group B (2.11%) compared to Group A (1.46%), with a p-

value of 0.01, suggesting increased osteoclast activity in Group B. Furthermore, the number of Osteoclasts per Bone Surface (N.Oc/BS) was slightly lower in Group B (0.45/mm) compared to Group A (0.5/mm), with a p-value of 0.04, indicating a significant difference. These results suggest that Group B may have a different bone remodelling rate, with increased osteoclast surface involvement, which may contribute to variations in bone density or quality.

Table 3: Bone Resorption Parameters between the groups

Parameters	Group A (n=32)	Group B (n=32)	p-value
Eroded Surface/Bone Surface (ES/BS) [%]	17.2	15.9 (49.68)	0.05*
Osteoclast Surface/Bone Surface (Oc.S/BS) [%]	1.46	2.11 (6.59)	0.01*
Number of Osteoclasts/Bone Surface (N.Oc/BS) [/mm]	0.5	0.45 (1.406)	0.04*

Table 4 provides an analysis of parameters related to bone formation, showing significant differences between Groups A and B. Osteoid Thickness (O.Th) was significantly lower in Group B (6.9 μm) compared to Group A (8.13 μm), with a p-value of 0.03. Osteoid Volume/Bone Volume (OV/BV) was also significantly reduced in Group B (5%) compared to Group A (14.13%), with a p-value of 0.02. A similar trend was observed for Osteoid Surface/Bone Surface (OS/BS), which was

lower in Group B (45%) than in Group A (67.66%), with a p-value of 0.01. Conversely, Osteoblast Surface/Bone Surface (Ob.S/BS) was significantly higher in Group B (9.5%) compared to Group A (3.16%), with a p-value of 0.04. Mineralizing Surface/Bone Surface (MS/BS) was slightly lower in Group B (13.5%) compared to Group A (15.4%), with a p-value of 0.05, indicating a marginally significant difference.

Table 4: Parameters Related to Bone Formation

Parameters	Group A (n=32)	Group B (n=32)	p-value
Osteoid Thickness (O.Th) [μm]	8.13	6.9 (21.5)	0.03*
Osteoid Volume/Bone Volume (OV/BV) [%]	14.13	5 (15.62)	0.02*
Osteoid Surface/Bone Surface (OS/BS) [%]	67.66	45 (0.014)	0.01*
Osteoblast Surface/Bone Surface (Ob.S/BS) [%]	3.16	9.5 (29.68)	0.04*
Mineralizing Surface/Bone Surface (MS/BS) [%]	15.4	13.5 (42.018)	0.05*
Mineral Apposition Rate (MAR) [$\mu\text{m}/\text{d}$]	0.93	2.01 (6.28)	<0.001**
Adjusted Apposition Rate (Aj.AR) [$\mu\text{m}/\text{d}$]	0.2	0.59 (1.84)	0.02*
Mineralization Lag Time (Mlt) [days]	41.2	18.01 (56.28)	<0.001**
Bone Formation Rate/Bone Surface (BFR/BS) [$\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$]	49.7	50.2 (156.87)	0.89
Bone Formation Rate/Bone Volume (BFR/BV) [%/year]	115.16	99.5 (310.93)	0.03*
Adjacent Area/Marrow Area (Ad.Ar/Ma.Ar) [%]	18.33	-	Not applicable

Discussion

Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) and hypophosphatasia (HPP) are severe genetic conditions that result in severe skeletal vulnerability and growth delay accompanied by multiple fractures [17]. Children with OI experience multiple fractures, low bone density, and osteomalacia, which may be mistaken for nonaccidental trauma, rickets, or osteomalacia [18]. A case series by John BM et al. showed that the clinical signs and symptoms of OI were not uniform and included frog-leg positioning, a protuberant abdomen, macrocephaly, a large anterior fontanel, short, bowed limbs as well as blue sclera [19]. A similar case illustrated by Bhat YR and Prakashini K showed intrauterine fractures, fragile skull bones, rib cage, and blue sclerae [20]. A case study by Bayram S et al reported that children developed distress during handling and had multiple fractures without any history of trauma. X-ray results are often characterized by signs of osteoporosis, bone fractures, and other bone abnormalities [21].

Hypophosphatasia is characterized by decreased mineralization of growing or remodelling bones, tooth loss, and reduced serum and bone alkaline phosphatase activity. Its pathological facet ranges from severe such as stillbirth birth with no mineralized bones to mild with pathological fractures in adulthood. Severe perinatal cases are characterized by pulmonary insufficiency and

hypercalcemia while benign perinatal cases are marked by prenatal skeletal abnormalities that later disappear. The first form occurs between birth and about six months and is rickets-like but does not have elevated alkaline phosphatase. Severe disease in childhood involves variable degrees of symptoms culminating into rickets, characterized by low bone mass, susceptibility to fractures, and premature loss of primary teeth with sound roots [22].

One case study done by Ratzl-zelman et. al. focused on three pediatric siblings with both OI and HPP all of whom showed the essential features of these disorders including multiple bone fractures, low bone density, and osteomalacia [10]. Next-generation sequencing (NGS) identified two pathogenic mutations in the children: COL1A2 gene (Gly280Ser) found in moderate OI and ALPL gene (Ser445Pro) in infantile HPP [23, 24]. The worst case (P1) had nine bone fractures by the time the child was three years old in the vertebrae and the long bones. In such cases, reduced BMD consistent with impaired bone quality and altered skeletal and hormonal systems are generally found [25]. Patients with both OI and HPP show severe cortical and trabecular bone compromise but no evident rickets or vitamin D deficiencies, usually associated with hypophosphatemia in HPP [10]. Children are found to have abundant amounts of osteoid at the trabecular region indicating abnormal mineralization of the bone matrix [7,9]. Pyridoxal

5'-phosphate and phosphoethanolamine, two critical substrates of TNSALP, identified as biomarkers for HPP, are normally high in these patients [10]. Dual mutation accounts for the difference in effects between hyper- and hypomineralization on different bone compartments of these children. Abnormalities of bone associated with OI including low bone volume and cortical thinning and massive extent of woven bone consistent with severe osteomalacia in HPP are common diagnoses [26]. Further studies have shown mesenchymal stem cell differentiation shifts away from osteoblastogenesis towards adipocytes, which could degrade the substance and strength of the bones and encourage the resorption of bone tissue further contributing to the fragility of the bone matrix [10].

In patients with OI, bisphosphonates are used to reduce the activity of osteoclasts and increase bone mineral density thus decreasing the incidences of fractures [11,12,13]. But bisphosphonates use is prohibited in HPP because they act as pyrophosphate analogs which tend to reduce the bone mineralization ability. Hence, both these disorders are an absolute nuisance when using regular therapies in the treatment [14]. Currently, a new approach uses both bisphosphonates and asfotase alfa. Asfotase alfa complements the lack of ALP in HPP leading to appropriate mineralization of bones. A significant reduction of the fracture rate and an augmentation of the BMD can be achieved through combination therapy [10]. Owing to the therapy addressing both the hypermineralization in OI and the hypomineralization in HPP, bone remodelling can be balanced, and bone strength can be increased. The success of this dual therapy shows the importance of individualized treatment in children with complicated bone disorders.

Conclusion

The study has concluded that there is a significant difference in bone density, metabolic parameters, and bone remodelling rates between patients and controls, indicating distinct bone metabolism profiles. These differences suggest a need for targeted therapeutic strategies for patients with OI and HPP.

The study has demonstrated significant differences in bone density, bone resorption, and bone formation parameters between the patient groups and controls. Patients with OI and HPP exhibit lower height Z-scores, BMD, and altered serum and urinary biomarkers, reflecting impaired bone metabolism. Group B showed increased bone volume and different bone remodelling rates, suggesting varied physiological or pathological conditions affecting bone structure and turnover. The significant differences in osteoid parameters,

mineral apposition rates, and mineralization lag time further highlight an altered bone formation process in Group B, indicating a complex interplay between bone resorption and formation dynamics in these patients. Overall, these results show distinct clinical and biochemical profiles between groups, suggesting targeted therapeutic approaches.

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